

Pathways of openness in NWL research: the case of Open Data

The Case of Open Data

Juliana E. Raffaghelli
Faculty of Education and Psychology
jraffaghelli@uoc.edu

Workshop Description

Open Science is an approach promoted by the European Commission that has been developing internationally for about ten years. In the field of research on NWL, however, the difficulties for opening up research have led to intrinsic, ongoing debates. A subtle aspect of this situation relates the poor appropriation and utilisation of scientific research products in the pedagogical field by potential users (stakeholders in the education and training system). As a matter of fact, educational data extracted from Learning Management Systems and Social Networks pose ethical problems as well as data literacy challenges both for the researchers (making data readable and usable) and the end users (reading and using data). Therefore, the specific case of Open Data (a relevant and innovative part of the Open Science scheme) should be discussed as a resource for NWL research. Data produced in this field is not limited to educational data-mining procedures, but encompasses a variety of research methodologies that yield diversified types of data, which in time implicates diversified ways of treating, sharing, and using them. Learning some of these principles and tools, and discussing them in the context of our current practices as researchers in the field of NWL, could be a starting point toward unraveling problems and coordinating efforts for further action.

Accordingly, the workshop will be organised in two simple phases:

- A. A conceptual introduction will provide the basis for understanding and discovering the principles, policy context, and existing practices relating to openness in overall research.
- B. A “hands on” activity in which participants will apply the above concepts to their respective NWL practices and research; participants will discuss both practical and deontological implications of their findings.

Intended Audience

This workshop deals with the issue of Open Science, with a focus on applying Open Data to research in networked learning (NWL). The workshop targets both researchers and practitioners interested in the use of raw Open Data coming out of NWL research.

Participant Engagement

Our approach to participant engagement will touch on multiple professional learning principles: significant knowledge that can be rapidly transferred to professional practice; reflection on prior knowledge and future practices; exploration of deontological positions; and the creation of a discipline/area of professional practice. While the workshop focuses on the participants' specific experiences and attempts to promote their professional learning, its results could also be seen as a springboard for the research community of educational technologies and NWL to reflect upon and discuss the principles and application of Open Science.

Along the process, we will adopt self-diagnosis tools on Open Science, an automatic response system, and Social Media to collect data and share reflections that will be opened to the research community.

Participant Outcomes

The workshop will aim to discover, reflect upon, and achieve concrete instruments to apply an Open Science perspective in NWL research.

Workshop Alignment with Conference Themes

The workshop's connections with the NWL field of research lies in two orders of issues:

- The workshop is a professional learning activity that will focus on a methodological debate within NWL research, which has relevance in the general context of the Open Science debate.
- The workshop will emphasize the idea that a participatory and open vision of research could align with open learning and pedagogical practices, toward more responsible and engaged scholarship. The possibility of adopting Open Science "products" as nodes or resources within a professional or educational network will also be addressed.

Workshop Process/Activities

1- Conceptual introduction [20 min]

Open Science will be defined as the research process that opens all research workflows, including design, tool and data generation, and publication in Open Access mode. An initial overview of the principles and tools of Open Science will be introduced, along with a few existing practices in other disciplines, including research in educational technologies and NWL. Special attention will be put toward understanding how openness in research could benefit “socially responsible research,” such as allowing citizens to access educational research projects. Some hypotheses will be presented to participants, with the goal of guiding their thought processes during phase two of the workshop.

RESOURCES

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Media Hashtags 	#ODNLC18
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop Presentation [QR code and link] 	#ODNLC18 Folder
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suggested readings [QR code and link] 	

2- Application of concepts and activities [70 min]

In order to delve deeper into the issues addressed above, the concept of Open Data and the processes of opening data will be explored as a fundamental element for transparency in NWL research. In practice, we will undertake the following activities:

Activity 2.1 – Exploring and discussing [35 min]

- A. Collecting personal reflections [15 min]
 - *In what way(s) can the concept Open Data be applied to our (workshop’s participants’) research projects?*

- *What are the critical issues that we face with regard to opening up research data to others?*
- *What are the critical issues that we face as researchers and practitioners relating to using Open Data?*
- *What is the feasibility of using Open Data as an open educational resource for further networked learning?*

B. The results will be undisclosed and discussed only within the general group [20 min].

RESOURCES

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool: Understanding my Open Research Practices [QR code and link] 	<p style="text-align: center;">Questionnaire</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Tool for Self-diagnosis 	<p>SPARC EUROPE - How Open is Your Research? A Checklist for Institutions</p> <p><i>...A warm thanks to Javiera Atenas (Open Knowledge Foundation) for having provided this resource!</i></p>

Activity 2.2 – Supporting practices [35 min]

- A. Participants will create a “Force Map” relating to the process of opening NWL data and research in their respective fields. [15 min]
- B. Discuss the decisions, instruments, and activities necessary to open the participants' research data within the context of the broader goal of Open Science. [20 min]

RESOURCES

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Worksheet: MyForce Map [QR code and link] 	<p>MyForceMap</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facebook Group [QR code and link] 	<p>Facebook Group</p>